

Grasping Learning for Service Robots

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Abstract—Service robotics is a fast-developing sector, requiring embedded intelligence into robotic platforms to interact with the humans and the surrounding environment. One of the main challenges in the field is robust and versatile manipulation in everyday life activities. An appealing opportunity to solve the mentioned task is to leverage on machine learning algorithms to let the robot adapt its behavior to unknown scenarios, defining the best strategy for a grasping and manipulation task in a trial and error process. In parallel, the mechanical design of compliant end-effectors able to adapt to the environment targets the same goal. These grippers represent a clever solution to the problems that arise when using sensorized hands with a high number of actuated joints, which are expensive and difficult to control. Within the described context, this work addresses the problem of finding the best position and joint configuration for a compliant, under-actuated, sensorless robotic hand to grasp an unforeseen deformable object based on collected RGB image and partial point cloud. A Bayesian approach to the problem of the optimization of the grasping strategy is proposed, enhancing it with transfer learning capabilities to exploit the acquired grasping knowledge to (partially) new objects. A PAL Robotics TIAGo (a mobile manipulator with a 7-degrees-of-freedom arm and an anthropomorphic underactuated compliant hand) has been used as a test platform, executing a pouring task while manipulating plastic (*i.e.*, compliant) bottles. The sampling efficiency of the data-driven learning is shown, compared to an evenly spaced grid sampling of the input space. In addition, the generalization capability of the optimized model is tested (exploiting transfer learning) on a set of plastic bottles and other liquid containers, achieving a success rate of the 88%.

Index Terms—Intelligent robotics, object manipulation, Bayesian optimization, service robotics, grasping.

I. PAPER CONTRIBUTION

The presented work is centered on the vision-based manipulation of non-rigid (*i.e.*, deformable) objects with a multi-fingered, underactuated, compliant, sensorless hand. The goal

is to train a robust and task-oriented grasping strategy, and to leverage on transfer learning (TL) to apply the acquired knowledge on objects that are unknown to the model. To tackle the target task, the authors propose an optimized learning approach, which allows to carry out the training directly on the robot (*i.e.*, experimentally). For this purpose, a BO-based algorithm [1] is presented and used in the optimization of the joint configuration and the grasp point of the object to be manipulated. BO is deemed the ideal candidate algorithm thanks to its sample efficiency, as a deep reinforcement learning approach would require an unbearable training time if not properly initialized. Such initialization can come neither from simulation, given the cumbersome work needed to simulate both the passive component of the hand behavior and the deformability of the objects, nor from imitation or kinesthetic learning, as the compliant hand could end up in very different configuration even if the same set of joint values is provided.

II. TASK DESCRIPTION

The final goal of this work is to endow a TIAGo robot with the grasping capability needed to pour water from a plastic bottle. The reason why this task has been selected is twofold:

- (I) it requires the functional manipulation of a non-rigid object;
- (II) it is a significant task for a robot providing assistance to frail people.

To further clarify the statement (II), the non-rigid behavior is the one shown by a common plastic bottle when squeezed. The *functional manipulation* of the bottle refers to the sequence of actions that are needed to actually pour the liquid in a glass/cup. Identifying a grasping strategy that satisfies the requirements is not trivial as the straightforward choice of

Fig. 1: The plots in the top line depict the distribution of the collected samples over the domain during a run of the corresponding optimization method. In (a), (b) and (c) the grasping strategies and the corresponding evaluations collected in the training of the individual models are shown, whereas in (d) the result of the evenly spaced exploration of the domain is reported. In the bottom line, the course of the penalty during the training procedure are shown: (e), (f), (g) report the results of the BO runs, and (h) the outcome of the grid search. The vertical dashed lines in (e), (f) and (g) demarcate the phases of the training (in order: initialization, first and second stage).

task outcome	P
failed to grasp	+100
failed to lift	+100
successful lift, fall during 45° tilt	-100
successful 45° tilt, fall during larger tilt	-150
successful 100° tilt, fall at repositioning	-200
successful task	-300

TABLE I: The value of the penalty function associated to each possible task outcome.

a very tight grasp results in the excessive squeezing of the bottle. This results in turn in the bottle slipping in the hand during the grasp and may lead to a deformation that would compromise the object’s functionality. On the other hand, not providing enough grasping force would not provide enough stability to fulfill the task.

To evaluate the performance of each set of parameters θ , defining a grasping strategy, a discrete penalty function P is defined. The optimization process has been designed as a minimization process, hence the values of P are distributed in a *the-lower-the-better* fashion, with negative values conceptually representing rewards. The resulting values of P are summarized in Table I.

III. RESULTS

In this section the quantitative evaluation of the performance of the optimization algorithm tested on the TIAGo robot is presented both in the training and validation procedure. A video is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SfT2lyhFuuQ>.

Figure 1 provides a visualization of the distribution of successful/unsuccessful strategies within the domain, and shows the course of the penalty function during the training of each one of the individual models and the grid search, conducted using bottle A as the object to grasp.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CURRENT/FUTURE WORKS

The results outlined in III demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed method in terms of the number of samples and hence required time for computation. The BO algorithm demonstrates to be efficient for the tuning of the grasping task, *i.e.*, guaranteeing adequate performance (achieving a success rate of the 88%) in a limited number of iterations (80 trials to train a grasping from scratch).

Future work should strive to increase the dimensionality of the problem, possibly until the 6 DoF defining the end-effector pose are encompassed in the optimized parameters. In addition, the bottle releasing strategy will be optimized in order to maximize its performance.

REFERENCES

[1] L. Roveda, M. Forgione, and D. Piga, “Robot control parameters auto-tuning in trajectory tracking applications,” *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 101, p. 104488, 2020.